

Research Article

Management Practices Involved in Fish Farming Operation in Four Local Government Areas of Kwara State

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Abstract

Management practices involved in fish farming operation cannot be overemphasized as it provides the basis for a successful fish farming business. In Nigeria, fish farming has a lot of practices existing along its production - supply chain that is not standardized. For optimum utilization of resources and increased production, productivity and returns to the farmer, improvement in the existing technology and practices are necessary. This survey was carried out to purposely assess the management practices carried out by fish farmers in four (4) Local Government Areas in Kwara State of Nigeria and thereby propose possible management practices that can further improve productivity. Thirty (30) fish farmers based on availability were surveyed in this study. The survey was carried out using a stratified sampling technique involving the use of a closed-ended questionnaire. The data contains information pertaining to sex, age, marital status, gender, household size, years of farming experience, level of education and the various management practices carried out. The SPSS statistical package of version 25.0.0.0 was used for data computation. Survey result revealed that we have a large number of educated fish farmers that falls within the age bracket of 31 – 40 years having a household size of 0 - 5 persons. The result further revealed that majority of the respondents had between 1 - 10 years of fish farming experience. Also, the management practices performed during fish farming operation revealed that majority of the fish farmers managed the water quality of their fish pond, clean their fish pond regularly, weed their fish pond surroundings, protect their fish ponds against predators, feed their fish routinely and provided measures for disease control. It was also observed in the study that regular sorting, growth monitoring, record keeping being aspects of fish farming management practices were not compromised. However, survey results concerning the use of liming and pond fertilization were not

commonly practiced among the fish farmers. This study also provided some useful recommendations that will assist in boosting fish production in Kwara State of Nigeria.

Keywords: management, practices, fish, pond, surroundings, feeding

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Introduction

Fish farming is an artificial routine of rearing fish for human utilization and yields a profitable means of livelihood for both rural and urban dwellers. According to Salau *et al.* (2014), it involves commercial rearing of fish in tanks or enclosures customarily for food.

In Nigeria, commercial fish farming was established over four decades ago. It plays a major role in attaining domestic and national food security and poverty reduction. Its position in the agricultural sector of Nigeria's economy is principal. Its contribution to the Gross Domestic Product increased from ₦76.76 billion in 2001 to ₦162.61 billion in 2005 (CBN, 2005).

Economically, fish farming has the capacity to increase into a large industry hence providing a route to an expanded business network in terms of supply services, farming and marketing, that may provide job opportunities to the teeming population. Fish farming also provides the chance to invest into feed mills, equipment manufacturing, processing, packaging and the provision of raw materials for the purpose of research and education (Okechi, 2004). Fish is a suitable source of high quality protein and other required nutrients. It has low calorie content and measure of cholesterol but is rich in protein.

Statistical studies have shown that the ongoing demand for fish in Nigeria put at over 1.5 metric tonnes has not been met which led to fish importation of about US\$ 400 million annually. Therefore, the demand for fish protein in Nigeria has surpassed the supplies leaving the general populace in sub optimal protein consumption (Oladimeji, 2017). According to a recent report published on Leadership Nigeria Newspaper of Friday, 20th September, 2019 stated that about 1.2 billion USD worth of fish was imported into Nigeria annually. He further explains that current fish production stood at 0.8 million tons while the demand was 2.7 million tons giving a deficit of 1.9 million tons.

In Nigeria, fish farming has a lot of practices existing along its production - supply chain that is not standardized. For optimum utilization of resources and increased production,

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productivity and returns to the farmer, improvement in the existing technology and practices are necessary. Bolorunduro (2010) reported that such improvement should aim at: (1) improving farm designs - for operational ease; (2) optimum soil and water condition; (3) removal of pest and predators; (4) qualitative and quantitative aspects of stocking fish seeds; (5) supplementary feeding; (6) soil and water quality management; (7) monitoring growth and health; and (8) improved methods of harvesting and post-harvest management (value-addition).

Kwara State possesses considerable potential for fish farming activities. The state is endowed with vast fertile land, water bodies and hatchery facilities that enhance fish farming, however, the information on management practices carried out by fish farmers has not been fully ascertained. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to assess the management practices involved in fish farming operations in four Local Government Areas of Kwara State and see possible ways to provide better management practices that can further improve fish production in the State.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in four Local Government Areas of Kwara State which include Ilorin Asa, Ilorin East, Ilorin South and Ifelodun. Figure 1 shows the map of the study area. According to Ndanusa *et al.* (2019), Kwara State is located in the North-Central part of Nigeria. It shares boundaries with Republic of Benin to the west and by the Nigerian States of Niger to the North, Kogi to the East, and Ekiti, Osun and Oyo to the South. Kwara State consists mostly of wooded savanna, but there are forested region in the South. Almost all of its savanna area was conquered by the Fulani in the early 19th century. Kwara is one of the least densely populated region in the country. Most of its inhabitants; chiefly Yoruba, Nupe, Busa and Baatonun people are Muslims engaged in farming yams, corn, sorghum, millet, onions, and beans are the most importantly staple crops; rice and sugarcane are significantly cash crops in the Niger floodplains.

Figure 1: Map of the Study Areas in Kwara State

KWARA Ministry of Agricultural Natural Resources (KWARA MANR, 2012) reported that Kwara is an ecological transition zone between the arid north and the moist south with temperature fluctuating between 30°C and 37°C in the year and rainfall of 1000 to 1500 mm annually. The State has two distinct climatic seasons, the wet (Rainy) and dry (Harmattan) seasons. The rainfall across the two seasons extends between November and February. This climatic condition as well as fertile soil makes the State favorable for arable crop production such as rice, millet, yam, cowpea etc.

Data collection

This research work was conducted to assess the management practices involved in fish farming operations in four Local Government Areas of Kwara State. Fish farmers were randomly selected from Asa, Ilorin South, Ilorin East and Ifelodun Local Government Areas of the State. The survey exercise was based on the number of available farmers into fish production in the selected LGAs. A stratified sampling technique was employed in administering a closed-ended questionnaire. Thirty questionnaires were administered based on availability and returned filled for data analysis. The returned filled questionnaires were thoroughly scrutinized by the fishery expert who is a Technical staff of the Centre.

Data collected on socio-economic characteristics output include age, marital status, gender, household size, years of farming experience and level of education. The administered questionnaire also contains questions on management practices carried out on the farmer's fish farms. Information on the management practices carried out were provided with four options, namely very often, often, rarely and not applicable.

Statistical tool

Data obtained from the respondents into fish farming business in the four Local Government Areas of Kwara State were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis involving frequency counts and percentage. The SPSS statistical package of version 25.0.0.0 was used for the data computation.

Results and Discussion

Socio-economic characteristics

Age

Thirty fish farmers were sourced based on availability within the four Local Government Areas of Kwara State. Out of these 30 fish farmers, 4 of them representing 13.33% were in the age bracket of 21 - 30 years, 12 of them representing 40% fell within the age bracket of 31 - 40 years, 9 of them representing 30% fell within the age bracket of 41 - 50 years and 5 of them representing 16.67% fell within the age bracket of 50 years and above. This signifies that youths within the age bracket of 31 - 40 years of age dominated the fish farming business in the four Local Government Areas surveyed in Kwara State.

Marital status

Among the 30 fish farmers surveyed, 24 of them representing 80% were found to be married, 5 of them representing 16.67% were single and 1 of them representing 3.33% was found to be a widow. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers in the area surveyed were married.

Gender

Out of the 30 fish farmers who responded to the questionnaires, 25 of them representing 83.33% were males while the remaining 5 representing 16.67% were females. This signifies that there are more male fish farmers than female fish farmers in fish farming business in the surveyed area.

Household size

Out of the 30 fish farmers, 15 of them representing 50% have a household size of 0 – 5 people, 9 of them representing 30% have a household size of 6 – 10 people, 1 of them representing 3.33% have a household size of 11 – 15 people, while the remaining 5 representing 16.67% of the fish farmers failed to declare their household size. This signifies that majority of the fish farmers involved in the study had a household size of 0 – 5 people.

Years of experience in fish farming

Twenty-seven (27) out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed representing 90% had between 1 - 10 years of fish farming experience while the remaining 3 fish farmers representing 10% had between 11 - 20 years of fish farming experience. This simply shows that almost all the farmers involved in the study area had between 1 – 10 years of fish farming experience.

Educational level

Out of the 30 fish farmers involved in the survey, 22 of them representing 73.33% had tertiary education, 4 of them representing 13.33% had high school education, while 1 respondent each representing 3.33% had primary education, adult education and no formal education, respectively. Also, one of the respondents representing 3.33% declined to give information related to his educational status. Almost all the fish farmers in the study area had tertiary education.

Management Practices performed during farm operation

Cleaning of ponds

Out of the 30 fish farmers involved in the study area, 10 of them representing 33.33% reported cleaning their ponds very often, 11 of them representing 36.67% reported cleaning their ponds often, 8 of them representing 26.67% reported rarely cleaning their pond while 1 of them representing 3.33% reported that cleaning of ponds was not applicable in his own case because he did not regard it as a usual management practice. This implies that majority of fish farmers clean their fish pond regularly.

Weeding of the fish pond environment

Three (3) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 10% reported carrying out weeding of the fish pond environment very often, 14 of them representing 46.66% reported carrying out weeding of the fish pond environment often, 2 of them representing 6.67% reported that weeding of the fish pond environment was rarely carried out, 8 of them representing 26.67% reported that weeding of the fish pond environment was not

applicable while three of them representing 10% failed to respond. This implies that larger a percentage of the fish farmers weed the surrounding of their fish pond environment.

Fish pond protection

Out of the 30 fish farmers surveyed in this study, 6 of them representing 20% reported protecting their fish ponds very often, fifteen of them representing 50% reported protecting their fish ponds often, six of them representing 20% reported rarely protecting their fish ponds, one of them representing 3.33% reported that fish pond protection was not applicable while two of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This means that majority of the fish farmers protect their fish ponds against predators.

Water quality maintenance

Out of the 30 fish farmers, nine of them representing 30% reported that water quality maintenance was carried out very often, fourteen of them representing 46.66% reported that water quality maintenance was carried out often, three of them representing 10% reported that water quality maintenance was rarely carried out while four of them representing 13.33% reported that water quality maintenance was not applicable. This means that majority of the fish farmers in the area under survey carried out water quality maintenance as part of their fish management practice.

Fertilization

Two (2) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 6.67% reported that pond fertilization was often carried out, seven of them representing 23.33% reported that pond fertilization was rarely carried out, 18 of them representing 60% reported that pond fertilization was not applicable in their own case because it was not a common practice observed in their area while three of them representing 10% failed to respond. Many of the fish farmers in the surveyed area did not apply fertilization in managing their fish pond.

Liming

Out of the 30 fish farmers involved in the surveyed area, two of them representing 6.67% reported carrying out liming activity very often in their fish farms, seven of them representing 23.33% reported carrying out liming activity often in their fish farms, 6 of them representing 20% reported rarely carrying out liming activity in their fish farms, eleven of them representing 36.66% reported that carrying out of liming activity in their fish farms was not applicable while four of them representing 13.33% failed to respond.

This implies that liming as a management practice under fish farming was not a common activity among the fish farmers in the surveyed area.

Feeding

Twenty-seven (27) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 90% reported feeding their fish very often, two of them representing 6.67% reported feeding their fish often while one of them failed to respond. This means that nearly all the fish farmers in the surveyed area fed their fish routinely.

Sorting

Sorting as the case may be is a very important management practice that involves the separation of bigger fish from the smaller fish inside the same fish pond for the purpose of preventing the bigger fish from eating the smaller fish. This is usually carried out once in a month. In view of this study, it was noticed that out of the 30 fish farmers involved in the surveyed area, nine of them representing 30% reported that sorting was carried out very often, fourteen of them representing 46.66% reported that sorting was carried out often, two of them representing 6.66% reported that sorting was rarely carried out, four of them representing 13.33% reported that sorting was not applicable while the remaining one respondent representing 3.33% failed to respond. This implies that a larger percentage of the fish farmers practiced sorting out of fish.

Growth monitoring

Ten of the farmers representing 33.33% reported that growth monitoring of fish was carried out very often in their fish farms, eleven of them representing 36.66% reported that growth monitoring of fish was carried out often in their fish farms, four of them representing 13.33% reported that growth monitoring was rarely carried out in their fish farms, another four of them representing same 13.33% reported that growth monitoring was not applicable in their fish farm while one respondent representing 3.33% did not respond to the question asked. This implies that a larger percentage of the fish farmers monitor the growth performance of fish in their fish farms.

Disease prevention and control

Among the fish farmers involved in the surveyed area, seven of them representing 23.33% reported providing disease prevention and control measures very often for their fish, ten of them representing 33.33% reported providing disease prevention and control measures often for their fish, nine of them representing 30% reported that they rarely provide disease prevention and control measures for their fish, two of them representing 6.67% reported that the activities involving the provision of prevention

and control measure for fish was not applicable while two of them representing 6.67% failed to respond. This implies that a larger percentage of the fish farmers in the study area provide disease prevention and control measures for their fish.

Record keeping

Fourteen (14) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 46.67% reported that record keeping as a management practice was carried out very often in their fish farms, 8 of them representing 26.66% reported that record keeping was carried out often in their fish farms, 2 of them representing 6.67% reported that record keeping was rarely carried out in their fish farms, 4 of them representing 13.33% reported that record keeping was not applicable in their fish farms while the remaining 2 representing 6.67% failed to respond. From this study, it can be concluded that record keeping is a management practice that is familiar to and carried out by the farmers in the area under survey.

Preservation techniques

This subsection intends to consider four preservation techniques involved in fish preservation management practices. These preservation techniques include refrigeration, smoking, drying and salting.

Refrigeration

One (1) out of the 30 fish farmers representing 3.33% reported that refrigeration was a preservation technique carried out very often in his fish farm, 3 of them each representing 10% reported that refrigeration was often and rarely carried out in their fish farms, respectively, 7 of them representing 23.33% reported that refrigeration was not applicable in their own case while 16 of them representing 53.33% did not respond because they do not refrigerate their fish as they sell them raw to their customers.

Salting

Out of the 30 fish farmers, 1 of them each representing 3.33% reported that salting of fish as a preservation technique was very often, often and rarely carried out in the fish farm, respectively, 5 of them representing 16.66% reported that salting of fish as a preservation technique was not applicable in their fish farms while the remaining 22 representing 73.33% did not respond because they do not add salt to their fish as they sell them raw to their customers.

Drying

Of the 30 fish farmers, one of them each representing 3.33% reported that drying of fish as a preservation technique was very often, often and rarely carried out in the fish farm,